

DORIVOR O'SIMLIKLARNING KIMYOVIY TARKIBI VA TASNIFI

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ABSTRACT

Ushbu maqolada xalq sog'lig'ini saqlash, kasalliklarning oldini olish, avlodlarni sog'lom qilib tarbiyalab yetishtirish masalalariga ahamiyat berar ekanmiz, o'z vaqtida va tez yuqori malakali tibbiy yordam ko'rsatish, kasallikni davolash va oldini olishning asosiy omillaridan biri bo'lmish yaxshi tao'sir etuvchi dorivor o'simliklar, ulardan olinadigan va tayyorlanadigan dori vositalari hamda boshqa vositalarni ko'plab yetkazib berishdagi imkoniyatlar yoritilgan..

Dorivor o'simliklarning organizmga ta'siri ularning tarkibidagi birikmalar miqdoriga bog'liq bo'lib, o'simlik qismlarida turli miqdorda to'planadi. Dorivor mahsulot tayyorlash uchun o'simlikning po'stloq, kurtak erta bahorda, barg o'simlik gullashi oldidan yoki gullaganda, gullari to'la ochilganda, meva va urug'lari pishganda, ildizi, ildizpoyasi, piyozi erta bahor yoki kech kuzda olinadi.

Shifobaxshlik xususiyatiga ega bo'lgan o'simliklar tarkibida uglevodorodlar, organik kislotalar, polisaxaridlar, kraxmal, oqsil, moy va moy kislotalari, efir moylari, alkaloid, tanid, saponin, glikozid, achchiq moddalar, fitonsidlar, mikroelementlar, vitaminlar, mineral tuzlar va boshqa moddalar bo'ladi

Dorivor o'simliklarni kimyoviy tarkibi. O'simliklarning kimyoviy tarkibi juda murakkab bo'lib, turli organik va mineral moddalardan tashkil topgan. Ularning hammasi ham dorivor bo'lmaydi va kasallikni davolashda shifobaxsh ta'sir ko'rsatmaydi. Ayrimlari esa dori turlarini tayyorlashda xalaqit beradi, shuningdek dorivor mahsulotlarni saqlash vaqtida ularning sifatini buzilishiga olib keladi yoki asosiy ta'sir etuvchi kimyoviy birikmalarni tez parchalanishga sababchi bo'ladi. Shuning uchun dorivor o'simliklar tarkibida uchraydigan moddalar tibbiyot nuqtayi nazardan 3 guruhga bo'linadi:

1. Dorivor o'simliklarning asosiy ta'sir etuvchi **biologik faol moddalari**. Dorivor mahsulot tarkibida kasalliklarni davolovchi terapevtik ahamiyatga ega bo'lgan biologik faol moddalari bo'lgani sababli u tibbiyotda va farmatsiyada ishlatiladi. O'simlikning terapevtik ahamiyati bo'lgan shifobaxsh biologik faol

kimyoviy birikmalari **asosiy ta'sir etuvchi moddalar** deb ataladi. Bu moddalar ko'pincha ayrim o'simliklarga xos bo'lgan alkaloidlar (belladonna, bangidevona, mingdevona, skopoliya turlariga xos atropin, giossiamin, skopalamin), glikozidlar (angishvonagul, strofant, adonis, marvaridgul, erizimum o'simliklariga xos yurak glikozidlari, rao'noguldoshlarga xos amigdal, karamdoshlarga xos sinigrin va boshqa izotiotsiantlar), kumarinlar, efir moylari, flavonoidlar, vitaminlar, lignanlar, oshlovchi va boshqa moddalar sifatida uchraydi.

2. O'simliklarning ta'sir etuvchi moddalar bilan **birga uchraydigan birikmalar**. Bunday moddalarni ayni shu o'simlikda terapevtik ahamiyati bo'lmasa-da, asosiy ta'sir etuvchi birikmalarning ta'sir kuchini o'zgartirishi (kuchaytirishi) hamda organizmga so'rilishi natijasida ta'sirini tezlatishi mumkin. Masalan, angishvonagul tarkibidagi steroid saponinlar shu o'simlikni asosiy ta'sir etuvchi birikmasi - yurak glikozidlarini organizmga so'rilishini tezlatib, mahsulotning dorivor preparatlari ta'sirini tezlatadi va kuchaytiradi.

3. Terapevtik ahamiyati bo'lmagan, **keraksiz, ballast moddalar**. Bu moddalar o'simliklarning asosiy ta'sir etuvchi va ular bilan birga uchraydigan birikmalar singari kimyoviy tuzilishi bo'yicha har xil moddalar bo'lishi mumkin. Uglevodlar, smolalar, efir moylari, yog'lar, organik kislotalar, oqsil, mineral va boshqa moddalar shular jumlasiga kiradi. Ular ma'lum sharoitda terapevtik ta'sirga ega bo'lgan birikma hisoblansa ham, boshqa o'simlikda ballast (keraksiz) modda sifatida uchrashi mumkin. Shuning uchun ballast moddalarni doimo bir xil, ma'lum guruhga kiradigan birikmalar deyish xato bo'ladi. Masalan, kanakunjut, zaytun, bodom va boshqalarning urug'idan olinadigan moylar asosiy ta'sir etuvchi birikmalar hisoblansa, shohkuya zamburugo'i hamda strofant urug'ida uchraydigan yog'lar shu o'simliklardan dori turlari tayyorlashda va mahsulotni saqlashda ballast modda hisoblanadi. Xuddi shuningdek, sano bargida smolalar, shohkuya tarkibida sut kislova ham ko'rsatilgan mahsulotlar uchun ballast moddalardir.

TADQIQOT NATIJALARI

Misol uchun bo'yoq moddalar o'rganildi. O'simlik organlari turli pigmentlarni, yani bo'yoqlarni saqlaydi. Ularga xlorofill, flavonoid, antotsian, karotinoid va boshqalar kiradi. *Xlorofill* yashil bo'yoq bo'lib, o'simlik organlarining yashil qismlarida uchraydi. Bu modda xlorofill "A" hamda xlorofill "B" ga bo'linadi. Xlorofill suvda parchalanmaydi, ammo yog'da parchalanadi. *Flavonoidlar* sariq rang degan so'zni anglatadi. Ular tabiiy murakkab birikmalardan bo'lib, benzo-U piron mahsuli hisoblanib, uning asosini fenil-propan tashkil etadi. Flavonoidlar, o'z navbatida, flavon, flavonoid, flavonol, katexin, antotsian kabi gruppalariga bo'linadi. *Antotsianlar* binafsha rangdan qizil ranggacha bo'lgan bo'yoq ko'rinishini beradi. Antotsianlar flavonli glikozidlar hisoblanib, gidrolizlanib, qand hamda aglikon-antotsianidninga parchalanadi. Ular o'z navbatida, keratsianin, enin va betaninlarga bo'linadi. Antotsianlar suvda yaxshi eriydi. Qizdirilsa yoki qaynatilsa tez buziladi, ya'ni rangi hamda xususiyatini yo'qotadi. Antotsianlar o'simliklarning guli, mevasi hamda urug'larida ko'proq bo'ladi. Tibbiyotda kvarsetin va rutin moddalaridan tayyorlanadigan dori-darmonlar ko'proq qo'llaniladi. Ular yurak-tomir, qon ketish, oshqozon yarasi, qon bosimi oshishi kabi xastaliklarga qarshi ishlatiladi.

XULOSA

Farmatsevtika sanoati, tibbiyotda, dorixonalar, Galen fabrika va laboratoriyalarini dorivor o'simlik mahsulotlari bilan ta'minlash, yovvoyi holda o'sadigan va o'stiriladigan dorivor

o'simlik mahsulotlari miqdorini ko'paytirish, yovvoyi holda o'sadigan dorivor o'simliklarni tabiiy sharoitda saqlab qolish, ularni muhofaza qilish va ko'paytirish, dorivor o'simliklarni davlat va jamoa xo'jaliklarida ko'plab ekish shular jumlasidandir.

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